

**28TH EAA ANNUAL MEETING
BUDAPEST, HUNGARY
31 AUGUST - 3 SEPTEMBER 2022**

ABSTRACT BOOK

ORGANISERS

PARTNERS

SPONSORS

HOW TO READ THE ABSTRACT BOOK

The Abstract Book is ordered by session numbers which were allocated during the session submission (i.e., the number sequence is discontinuous).

Author's affiliation is stated in brackets following the author's name; where authors share the same affiliation, it is only stated once.

Index of Authors includes all session organisers and only the main authors of contributions.

Please note that names, titles and affiliations are reproduced as submitted by the session organisers and/or authors. Language and wording of titles and abstracts are not revised.

28th EAA Annual Meeting (Budapest, Hungary, 2022) – Abstract Book

Technical editing: Kateřina Kleinová (EAA)

Design and layout: Kateřina Kleinová (EAA)

Design cover page: Aliz Ertler

ISBN: 978-80-88441-02-1

European Association of Archaeologists

Prague, July 2022

© European Association of Archaeologists, 2022

**28TH EAA ANNUAL MEETING
(BUDAPEST, HUNGARY, 2022)**

ABSTRACT BOOK

378	Moving beyond the Fact of Mobility? Re-evaluating the Strengths and Limitations of Strontium Isotope Analyses in Archaeology	711
379	The Archaeology of Large-scale Conflicts: The Emergence of the Mongol Empire and the Invasion of Central-Europe in its Eurasian Context.....	720
380	Can you Future Proof Skill Development Work in Archaeology?	721
381	Waterscapes: Traces of Interaction between People and Water from Neolithic to Bronze Age Europe	722
382	Technology, Risk, and Change	727
383	Scaling up: Archaeological Science Contributions to Big-picture Narratives on Human-Animal Relations	731
384	Women's Status and Agency in the Neolithic and Metal Ages of Central Europe [AGE]	732
385	Place Name and Archaeology – New Interdisciplinary Approaches in Europe	737
388	Towards an Open Platform for Computer Simulations of Past Socio-ecological Systems.....	741
389	Moving into the Mediterranean – New Developments in the Research on Genetics, Mobility, Culture Change and Languages.....	741
390	All on Walls. Current Issues on Historical Wall Painting Science, Conservation, and Restoration	747
392	The Anti-HABI Toolkit: Practical Solutions and Measures for Preventing and Addressing Harassment, Assault, Bullying and Intimidation in Archaeology [AGE]	752
394	So Many Settlements so Few Graves? Neolithic and Chalcolithic Practices with the Dead in Circum Pontic Region and Southeastern Europe	754
395	Medieval Stone Monuments: Reuse and (Re)Integration	757
396	Reenactment and Living Museum – Make History Accessible	759
397	Archaeological Prospection and Field Evaluation Practice from Bologna Process to Convention of La Valetta. Do We Practice What We Preach? [Archaeological Prospection]	764
399	Linking Databases for Comparing Research: Do We Need a European Hillfort Information System? [COMFORT]	769
400	Step by Step. The Rough Road towards Community Archaeology.....	769
401	To Use or Not to Use: 3D Documentation in Fieldwork and in the Lab [3D-Archaeology]	772
402	Scaling Bronze Age Societies – Between the Micro and Macro	776
403	Domestication of Space: Internal and External Dwelling Structures in Middle and Upper Palaeolithic Sites [PaM] ...	779
404	Socio-environmental Systems and Resilience to Disturbance Regimes	781
405	"The Grass Is Always Greener on the Other Side?" The Benefit of the Local and Regional Lithic Raw Materials	785
406	Ancient and Traditional Crafts in Changing Environments: Addressing the Needs for Temporal Perspectives	786
407	Digital Religioscapes: Current Methodologies and Novelities in the Analysis of Sacr(aliz)ed Spaces.....	790
416	Challenging Island Archaeology with the Third Science Revolution	794
417	As Far as Vases Go: Studies on Ancient Greek Pottery Trade and Its Contexts.....	801
419	Using Forensic Archaeological Approaches to Inform the Past	807
420	EAA Community for Climate Change and Heritage (CCH) Roundtable.....	814
421	Space Syntax: The Material Imprints of Spatial Integration Processes	814
422	'... In with the New!': The Future of Archaeological Research in Medieval Europe	818
424	Actors, Not Spectators. Community Representation in Archaeology and Cultural Heritage in the 21st century.....	819
426	From Isotope Ratios to Narratives: Exploring the Ways that Biogeochemical Studies are Impacting Eurasian Archaeology	823
427	Prehistoric Histories: Linking Individual Agency and Broad Transformations.....	828
430	Percussive Osseous Industry a Human Revolution between Pre-formation and Waste Selection [PaM].....	830
432	Logistics and Natural Resources: Supply and Transportation through Time (5th century BC – 5th century AD).....	833
434	Creation of European Identities – Food, Textiles and Metals in the Iron Age Between Alps, Pannonia and Balkans	836
436	General session	839
437	Reintegration in Medieval Archaeology (MERC Forum)	844
438	Europe's medieval past: a manifesto (MERC Round table).....	844
	Index of session organisers and authors.....	848

DOMESTICATION OF SPACE: INTERNAL AND EXTERNAL DWELLING STRUCTURES IN MIDDLE AND UPPER PALAEOLITHIC SITES [PAM]

Theme: 5. Climate Change and Socioenvironmental Perspectives

Organisers: PEAN, Stéphane (Muséum national d'Histoire naturelle, UMR 7194 HNHP) - Shydlovskyi, Pavlo (Taras Shevchenko National University of Kyiv, Department of Archaeology and Museology) - Mester, Zsolt (Eötvös Loránd Tudományegyetem BTK Régészettudományi Intézet)

Format: Regular session

The structuration of the settlement area is a bright feature of Middle and Upper Palaeolithic campsites. Different occupation characteristics can be identified by the functional specifications of distinct archaeological structures, in relation to the palaeoecological framework and the dynamics of settlement development over time.

Dwellings and constructional materials, pits (storage or dumping), hearths, activity areas, such as workshops or butchering zones, demonstrate the spatial arrangement of residential practices in different sectors. Their study requires interdisciplinary research to establish their chronological and functional relationships and the insertion of the settlement in the surface microrelief and local landscape features. The analysis of separate structures with functional peculiarities from Middle and Upper Palaeolithic campsites allows to reconstruct the interaction of inhabitants with the surrounding landscape, to understand the links between different types of activity inside the settlement area, to establish functional and seasonal characteristics of occupation and to identify behavioural features of Palaeolithic settlers.

The session gives the opportunity to connect new researches on dwelling structures from Middle and Upper Palaeolithic sites through Europe, and interpretative studies of spatial behaviour, in relation with specific landscape, palaeo-ecological and cultural features.

4 INTERNAL AND EXTERNAL STRUCTURES OF THE UPPER PALAEOLITHIC DWELLING NO.4 FROM MEZHYRICH SETTLEMENT (UKRAINE)

Abstract author(s): Shydlovskiy, Pavlo (Taras Shevchenko National University of Kyiv; Muséum national d'histoire naturelle, UMR 7194 HNHP; Centre for Paleoethnological Research) - Péan, Stéphane (Muséum national d'histoire naturelle, UMR 7194 HNHP) - Tsvirkun, Ostap (National Museum of the History of Ukraine; National University of Kyiv-Mohyla Academy; Centre for Paleoethnological Research) - Chymyrys, Marharyta (Taras Shevchenko National University of Kyiv; Centre for Paleoethnological Research) - Dudnyk, Diana (Institute of Archaeology of the NAS of Ukraine; Centre for Paleoethnological Research)

Abstract format: Oral

Mezhyrich is a Late Upper Palaeolithic settlement in Middle Dnieper basin (Ukraine), which belongs to the Epigravettian cultural complex and dates to 15-14.4 ka 14C BP. Four mammoth bone dwellings have been discovered through long-term research since the mid-1960's.

In 2018, investigations of the interior space of unit Dwelling 4 were resumed. It was found that the bones that make up the structure form such elements as the basement (regularly dug in a circle of mammoth skulls and long bones), outer cladding (flat, long bones, and mandibles), cover bones (tusks and scapulae that fell inside the structure). A study of the interior space of the dwelling revealed differences in the lithic and faunal composition in different areas

of the filling. A lithic workshop was found in the north-eastern part. In the opposite SW part, relative to a central hearth, the remains of medium-sized mammals were found in anatomical order together with a series of tools for leather processing. The complexity of the internal filling of dwelling is complemented by the presence of at least three surfaces with a subhorizontal location of the findings. In previous years, two cultural layers were found in the adjacent area, as well as several functionally different structures surrounding the dwelling: pits, workshops, areas of dense cultural layer. Current research, together with the previously established multi-layered nature of the Mezhyrich site, proves the periodicity of the residents' stay in the settlement.

The whole settlement structure of Mezhyrich site consists of four spatial units. Each unit consists of functionally different structures located around a mammoth bone dwelling and in different archaeological horizons and should be considered as a complex dynamic structure that characterizes the interaction of a small social group with the local landscape.